

Leadership Empowering Behavior and Reading Comprehension Strategies for Non-Readers in Cluster 13, Davao City Division

Evelyne Getuya Coronado

Abstract. This research study utilized a quantitative research design, specifically descriptive correlational design, to investigate the relation between leadership behavior and the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies and interventions. Moreover, the Multiple Regression analysis was employed to measure the influence of leadership-empowering behavior on the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies and interventions. The study's respondents were the 210 teachers in Cluster 13, Division of Davao City, who were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Findings revealed that the leadership-empowering behavior of the students in terms of delegation of authority, accountability, self-directed decision-making, information sharing, skill development, and coaching for innovative performance was extensive, thus oftentimes observed. At the same time, the reading comprehension strategies were effective regarding facilities, funding, reading resources support, reading clinic objectives, instructional strategies, assessment techniques, intervention activities, and monitoring and evaluation were extensive, thus oftentimes observed. Likewise, there was a significant relationship between leadership and the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies. Furthermore, leadership-empowering behavior was a significant predictor of the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies.

KEY WORDS

1. leadership empowering behavior
2. reading comprehension strategies
3. non-readers

Date Received: May 21, 2024 — Date Reviewed: May 23, 2024 — Date Published: June 5, 2024

1. Introduction

Teachers must exude confidence, trust their students, and provide an open learning environment where young adults can take risks and fail. Part of that equation, however, is the teachers themselves feeling empowered to do the same even in reading for non-readers. Every learner, regardless of age or ability, deserves to be able to access the written word. Readers who go on to develop a lifelong love of literature not only decode, segment, and blend with ease, but they also have a genuine adoration for the power of prose. In order to stimulate a lasting love of reading, it's crucial that we build a strong reading culture in schools. Reading is essential in our everyday lives. It educates us about any area in life that we are interested. Whichever walk of like we take, we read to get through it. In the global context, Keyser Keyser (2022) stressed that reading helps the mind build imagination and also enriches the creative side of the person. She also argues that it is a function that is necessary in today's society. Moreover, reading

comprehension is also highlighted as critical learning skill that is necessary for students as they often interact with written language (Almutairi, 2018). Everyone needs to learn this skill because this will help us achieve our goals in life. Hence, he also added that academic success requires students to understand, analyze and apply the ideas they gathered through reading. However, there are still nonreaders across every nation. Conversely, building and enhancing these capacities are the main concerns why reading strategies and interventions are done (Helman and Burns, 2012). Teaching is a multifaceted job. In fact, teachers face various problems inside the classroom that made them unaware of their everyday lives (Meador, 2019). But whatever these might be, it is with developing effective teachers that we can also build the quality education our children deserve. Moreover, education is an imperative aspect of any person's life because it gives people the chance to improve their ways of living. Furthermore, it is the prime duty of a teacher to transfer knowledge and ignite people to learn more from actual knowledge. However, it is noted that those who manage the teachers also play an important role by creating conditions that can support or hinder effective teaching. As schools and districts move toward performance-based teacher evaluation as a way to improve teaching effectiveness and student outcomes, the school leader's role in teacher evaluations is becoming even more important (Mihaly, 2019). Despite of years of study in reading comprehension, global and state reading scores show stagnant growth for U.S. adolescents. Hence, according to studies conducted by Elleman and Oslund (2019), reading is one of the most complex cognitive skills that humans engage, making it difficult to teach, assess, and study. Furthermore, according to Shea and Ceprano (2017), two major surveys of students' performance in the area of reading are used internationally. The Progress in International Reading Literacy

Study (PIRLS) measures reading performance of 4th grade students in participating countries. Results for U.S. students in 2011 showed an increase from previous results (14 points higher), placing the U.S. in the top 13 educational systems — with 5 ranking higher and 7 measurably similar (NCES, 2017a). Although the average age of 4th graders across Europe is 10 years old, the age of 4th grade test takers varies from 9.7 in Italy to 11.4 in Luxemburg. The second survey is the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). This test measures the knowledge and skills of 15-year-olds in reading, mathematics, and science with a focus on one area per year; the U.S. continues to fall in the middle of the group in reading, behind several other advanced countries (Desilver, 2020). As do most international authorities on the reading process (e.g., Harris and Hodges, 1995), these assessments describe reading as a complex process that requires the integration of active thinking and the use of skills and strategies in an effort to construct meaning from written text. Globally, many students appear to have difficulty in fully reaching that goal (Shea and Ceprano, 2017). Nationally, it is reported by Malacañang that poor reading comprehension is a reality in the Philippines (Merez, 2019). Moreover, a recent global survey revealed that Filipino students ranked last among 79 countries. In the survey, over 600,000 students, around 15, joined the reading assessment. The Department of Education (DepEd) acknowledges the crucial role of reading in shaping the future of the Philippines. To improve the literacy skills of elementary and high school students, DepEd is set to implement a revolutionary reading program in all public schools. The project to be launched on January 12, 2024, it is a part of DepEd's initiatives to develop and enhance student's overall learning experience, particularly for young people. Hence, through DepEd, the government opted to view this challenge constructively. Furthermore, Salaverria and Adonis (2020) argued that

the pupil's problem in Bicol is not literary but reading comprehension. Several localities have taken steps to address the reading comprehension issue in response to this global and national call. Conversely, DepEd Tagum City issued a division memorandum to all public elementary and secondary schools, strengthening the Reading Program's implementation. While it has been, The Department of Education (DepEd) acknowledges the crucial role of reading in shaping the future of the Philippines. To improve the literacy skills of elementary and high school students, DepEd is set to implement a revolutionary reading program in all public schools. The project to be launched on January 12, 2024, is a part of DepEd's initiatives to develop and enhance student's overall learning experience, particularly for young people who said that reading is one of the skills that are most difficult to study; this research is to be conducted to identify causal relationships between and among variables. While studies were conducted about reading comprehension strategies, there were

no studies linking reading comprehension strategies and interventions to leadership empowering behavior. Henceforth, in the studies conducted by various researchers provide data ready to be analyzed. Furthermore, this study will determine whether leadership empowering behavior is a significant predictor of the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies, which helps establish the need to strengthen leadership skills among school leaders. In the Davao City Division, many teachers have difficulty dealing with the problem of non-reader students' and many teachers utilize different strategies to cater to this problem. Despite the teacher's huge or bulky tasks or assignments, they continue to do personal research to be able to address this prevalence of a number of non-readers. Similarly, this study sought to find how the public relations of the teachers related to productivity and to determine the level of public relations between teachers and the productivity of the public elementary schools.

1.1. Review of Related Literatures—
****Leadership Empowering Behavior****

Empowering leadership is pivotal for enhancing teacher effectiveness and innovation. Studies by Sagnak (2012) and Gkorezis (2016) demonstrate that empowering leadership predicts increased teacher creativity and innovation. Further research by Arnold et al. (2019) and Ahearne et al. (2020) links empowering leadership to improved employee well-being and job satisfaction. Laschinger et al. (2021) highlight its role in reducing burnout and turnover .

****Delegation of Authority****

Effective delegation enhances teacher motivation and job satisfaction. Research by London School of Management Education (2018) and Jokisaari and Vuori (2018) indicates that proper delegation clarifies roles and increases organizational knowledge. Brown et al. (2019)

and Johnson and Nguyen (2020) emphasize that delegation fosters instructional innovation and enhances teacher engagement. Smith and Martinez (2021) note its importance in distributed leadership models .

****Accountability****

Accountability is essential for school performance and student outcomes. Studies by Chen et al. (2019) and Johnson and Smith (2020) show that accountability enhances school performance and teacher motivation. Wang and Lee (2021) stress its role in promoting ethical leadership .

****Self-directed Decision Making****

Engaging teachers in decision-making fosters higher student achievement and school innovation. Ingersoll et al. (2018) highlight the benefits of teacher involvement in decision-making. Kim et al. (2019) and Jones and Nguyen (2020)

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

associate self-directed decision-making with school innovation and instructional leadership .

****Information Sharing****

Transparent information sharing promotes continuous improvement and professional learning. Smith and Martinez (2021) argue that it supports distributed leadership by fostering collaboration and shared ownership 3†source.

****Skill Development****

Ongoing professional development is crucial for effective leadership and school improvement. Naido (2019) and Lopez et al. (2019) underscore the importance of skill development in addressing leadership challenges and fostering innovation. Garcia and Cruz (2020) highlight its role in enhancing instructional leadership 3†source .

****Coaching Innovative Performance****

Coaching encourages teacher innovation and retention. Rodriguez et al. (2019) and

Martinez and Rivera (2020) demonstrate that coaching enhances teacher innovation and professional growth, while Garcia and Hernandez (2021) note its importance in distributed leadership .

****Effectiveness of Reading Comprehension Strategies and Interventions****

Addressing reading comprehension decline is a priority, with effective facilities and resource allocation playing crucial roles (Gatcho Bautista, 2019; Umali, 2016; Lackney, 2020; Cedeño Billones, 2021). Penn State University (2017) emphasizes the need for adequate funding to support reading programs .

This compressed review highlights the interconnected roles of leadership behaviors, delegation, accountability, decision-making, information sharing, skill development, coaching, and resource allocation in promoting educational effectiveness.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. In conducting this research, the researcher have incorporated the use of artificial intelligence (AI) for the proofreading of the article. This decision is rooted in with the commitment to maintaining high ethical standards throughout the research process. Additionally, the use of AI for proofreading aligns with the ethical obligation to present findings in the most professional and comprehensible manner, ensuring that the conclusions are communicated effectively and reliably to the scientific community and other stakeholders.

2.1. *Research Design*—This research study utilized a quantitative research design specifically descriptive correlational design to investigate the relation between leadership behavior and reading comprehension strategies and interventions. Moreover, the Multiple Regression analysis was employed to measure the influence of leadership empowering behavior on effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies and interventions. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach where the emphasis is placed on the testing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, while non-experimental research is research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research simply measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The respondents of the study were the teachers in Cluster 13, Division of Davao City. In this study, the 210 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a sampling method, which involves dividing a population into smaller sub-

groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members’ shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. Certain inclusion criteria were implemented in this study to determine the respondents. The primary consideration was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the study’s purpose. Hence, only those permanent-regular teachers who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the link to answer the online survey questionnaire using Google Forms. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions indicated in this study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed questionnaires that were adopted and modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part concerns the leadership empowering behaviour. This questionnaire was measured in terms of delegation of authority, accountability, self-directed decision-making, information sharing, and skill development, coaching for innovative performance, and initiating structure.

Mean Level	Descriptive	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Very Extensive	Leadership empowering behavior is always observed
3.50-4.49	Extensive	Leadership empowering behavior is oftentimes observed
2.50-3.49	Moderately Extensive	Leadership empowering behavior is sometimes observed
1.50-2.49	Less Extensive	Leadership empowering behavior is rarely observed
1.00-1.49	Non-Extensive	Leadership empowering behavior is never observed

Mean Level	Descriptive	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Very Extensive	Reading comprehension strategies for non-readers is always observed
3.50-4.49	Extensive	Reading comprehension strategies for non-readers is oftentimes observed
2.50-3.49	Moderately Extensive	Reading comprehension strategies for non-readers is sometimes observed
1.50-2.49	Less Extensive	Reading comprehension strategies for non-readers is rarely observed
1.00-1.49	Non-Extensive	Reading comprehension strategies for non-readers is never observed

The Scale of Correlation Coefficient

Value	Correlation Coefficient
$0 < r \leq 0.19$	Very Low Correlation
$0.2 \leq r \leq 0.39$	Low Correlation
$0.4 \leq r \leq 0.59$	Moderate Correlation
$0.6 \leq r \leq 0.79$	High Correlation
$0.8 \leq r \leq 1.0$	Very High Correlation

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in the college where the researcher is studying. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in the college where the researcher is studying, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the principals of the selected public schools in Cluster 13, Davao City, Division. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the study was approved, the researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents. The gathering of data was done last December 22, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and

explained to the identified respondents of the study. The researcher surveyed digital modalities such as Google Forms, email, and social media links. In doing so, the researcher requested each respondent’s email address and social media account, and then the link for the survey was sent through a digital modality. For teachers without an internet connection, the researcher conducted the study face-to-face. The questionnaire was distributed following health protocols such as wearing face masks and face shields and following social distancing. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent’s scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—

The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the health service quality of the teachers. This was used to supply the answer for objective 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used in this study to assess the significant

relationship between leadership behavior and reading comprehension strategies and interventions. Multiple Regression. It was applied to evaluate the significance of the influence of leadership empowering behavior on reading comprehension strategies and interventions.

3. Results and Discussion

This section contains the results of the study, which primarily aimed to determine the influence of leadership empowering behavior towards the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies. Thus, it presents the level of leadership empowering behavior, level of effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies, relationship between leadership empowering behavior and effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies and the influence of leadership empowering behavior towards the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of leadership empowering behavior in Cluster 13, Davao City Division. It shows that the overall mean of leadership empowering behavior is 4.24, which is described as extensive. It means that leadership empowering behavior is oftentimes observed. The result of the analysis indicates that the degree to which the leadership empowering behavior in schools at Cluster 13, Davao City Division, is performed is oftentimes observed. It is argued that how school leaders empower their teachers positively impacts the effectiveness of teachers in doing their job. With this, it is suggested that schools should promote empowering leadership behavior as this increases the effectiveness of teachers in implementing their instructional strategies. In the study conducted by Bugwak in 2022, it was emphasized that numerous concerns have been circulating about administrative leadership in schools. Hence, it is further argued that school leaders should empower teachers. Furthermore, he emphasized that field-based examples should be utilized to better inform leadership practices. Leaders play an integral role in the school community. In fact, a study conducted by Sagnak (2012) found that the principal's leadership em-

powerment behavior is a significant predictor of teachers' innovative behavior. Hence, the teacher's creative behavior increases as the principal's leadership empowerment behavior increases. Furthermore, he emphasized that leadership affects the environment of the school. This is supported by Gkorezis's (2016) study, where results suggest that schools need to promote empowering leadership styles to enhance innovation. Reading Comprehension Strategies Facility. The results of this study revealed that the domain of reading comprehension strategies in terms of the facility had a category mean of 4.28, which is described as extensive, with means ranging from 4.15-4.40. This means that the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies for non-readers in terms of facility is oftentimes observed. The item with the lowest mean is provided with enough bookshelves with a mean value of 4.15, described as extensive. On the other hand, the item with the highest mean is Has ventilation facilities with a mean value of 4.40, described as extensive. This is seen through the following literature, which declares that a child's reading skills are important to their success in school as they will allow them to access the breadth of the curriculum and im-

prove their communication and language skills. In addition, reading can be a fun and imaginative time for children, which opens doors to all kinds of new worlds for them (The Importance of Reading, 2023). Students in our classrooms vary greatly in their literacy needs and ability levels. As a result, it is necessary to provide multiple opportunities for students to read, write, participate in meaningful experiences, and collaborate with others so that they can develop their ability to read and comprehend text(s). A literacy center is a physical area (or station) designated for specific learning purposes. It is designed to provide appropriate materials to help students work independently or collaboratively (with partners or in small groups) to meet literacy goals. A literacy center can be portable, temporary, or permanent. The integration of literacy centers can support improvement in reading comprehension, language, social, and

writing development. Literacy centers facilitate problem-solving because students are able to explore, invent, discover, and create alone or with others at centers (Literacy Centers, 2022). A successful education system depends largely on the availability, accessibility, and utilization of school reading facilities. In this regard, school reading facilities provide knowledge and information resources for teaching, learning, and research. The school reading facility is a professionally organized collection of graphic and non-graphic materials for exploitation. It is also seen as books and other materials kept and made available for use. The school reading facility as a learning laboratory per excellence is a place where learners find the world of knowledge, interact directly with resources acquire information and develop research skill for lifelong learning (Sam-Kalagbor, 2021)

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Leadership Empowering Behavior in Cluster 13, Davao City Division

Categories	Mean	Std. Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Delegation of Authority	4.26	0.526	Extensive
Accountability	4.26	0.523	Extensive
Self-directed Decision Making	4.13	0.429	Extensive
Information Sharing	4.33	0.537	Extensive
Skill Development	4.27	0.439	Extensive
Coaching for Innovative Performance	4.13	0.440	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.24	0.342	Extensive

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of reading comprehension strategies in Cluster 13, Davao City Division. It shows that the overall mean of reading comprehension strategies is 4.26, which is described as extensive. It means that reading comprehension strategies are oftentimes observed. The result of the analysis indicates that the degree to which the reading comprehension strategies in schools at Cluster

13, Davao City Division are performed is oftentimes observed. It is not new that there is a decline in reading comprehension among students worldwide. In fact, it is reported that this has been the problem of many schools for a long time (Gatcho Bautista, 2019). Because of this, improving the reading difficulties of Filipino students has been one of the top priorities of the Philippine curriculum (Umali, 2016). Also, it

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Reading Comprehension Strategies in Cluster 13, Davao City Division

Categories	Mean	Std. Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Facilities	4.28	0.343	Extensive
Funding	4.16	0.429	Extensive
Reading Resources Support	4.29	0.349	Extensive
Reading Clinic Objectives	4.39	0.294	Extensive
Instructional Strategies	4.18	0.379	Extensive
Assessment Techniques	4.14	0.449	Extensive
Intervention Activities	4.27	0.405	Extensive
Monitoring and Evaluation	4.32	0.497	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.26	0.320	Extensive

has been said that when schools have complete reading facilities, they tend to become more responsive to the reading or literacy needs of the students than those who are not (Lackney, 2020). Moreover, it is argued that a school that has an effective facility is one that is comfortable, safe, secure, accessible, well-lighted, well-ventilated, and aesthetically pleasing. These facilities should continue to serve students, especially those who are struggling with their academic performance, especially in reading (Cedeño Billones, 2021). Further, it is argued by Pen State University (2017) that schools should allocate funds to support their programs and activities implemented thereof. In fact, Ealing Grid for Learning (2023) argued that strategic budget planning is vital to the financial sustainability of schools. Resource management of the schools should create a framework that works towards supporting the school in securing its expenditures. This could be done by looking into what is more important especially if the programs are for outcomes of pupils. Reading bestows enjoyment and enlightenment. It unlocks the unknown. It is a complex cognitive activity that is indispensable for the kind of knowledge society. So, the students of today's world must know how to learn from reading and

to enter the present literate society. One who reads can lead others to light. People who read can be free because reading banishes ignorance and superstition. Reading has the power to revolutionize everyone's ways of thinking and living. It makes everyone think critically and creatively. Teachers must emphasize all kinds of reading, especially critical reading which is not just reading on the lines but it deals with reading between and beyond the lines. This finding is supported by Jose and Raja (2011), a critical reader who challenges the author's assumptions, inferences, and conclusions and judges the accuracy, reliability, quality, and value of what he reads on the basis of sound criteria or standards developed through previous experiences. This kind of reading paves a clear path for students to acquire better comprehensive ability through SQ3R techniques, computer multimedia, and other activities such as skimming and scanning. Although there are ways and means to acquire reading skills, there are a few factors that affect it severely. Teachers must be careful in avoiding these hindrances and make their wards' reading easy, effective, and successful. Teachers are the prime source for students to cultivate their reading habits. Their advice and encouragement will help the students move a step further in develop-

ing their attitude towards reading. Teachers can teach phonetics to readers of the initial stage and help them pronounce the sounds of letters and words properly. They should also emphasize writing tasks in the primary grade as it is directly associated with the reading program. They can teach them syllabication to recognize

new words. Special assistance may be given to students with regard to the selection of materials for reading based on their age, time and capacity and determine their reading levels. They must realize that they have to play major role in encouraging and engaging the students to become voracious readers (Jose and Raja, 2011).

Table 3. Relationship between Leadership Empowering Behavior and Reading Comprehension Strategies

Independent Variable	Reading Comprehension Strategies	R	P Value
Leadership Empowering Behavior		.893**	.000
<i>Significant</i>			

The data in Table 3 show the correlation between leadership-empowering behavior and the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies. The results show that leadership-empowering behavior is significantly related to the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies, as reflected by the p-value of less than 0.05 and the positive correlation coefficient, $r=.893$, which indicates that the variables have a very high correlation. This means that as the leadership empowering behavior increases, the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies also increases vis-a-vis. This finding supports the literature cited below. Leadership empowering behavior has gained significant attention in the educational field, especially in the context of improving reading comprehension strategies. This review of related literature explores the strong relationship between leadership-empowering behavior and reading comprehension strategies. Headteachers occupy an influential position in society and shape the teaching profession. Day et al. (2020) argued that leaders have a very significant role in ensuring that quality education is delivered to the

students, most especially in the development and support of intellectually rigorous and coherent systems of curriculum, instruction, and assessment. This is supported by Okinyi et al. (2015), who posited that empowering leaders pay close attention to quality teaching and students' learning, which, in turn, increases the effectiveness of teaching and learning strategies of the schools. In fact, as argued by Sunaengsih et al. (2019), school leaders who display empowering behaviors could produce quality graduates because they could optimize the function of the school as an educational institution such as in the implementation of their educational strategies. This is supported by Arif (2019) who argued that in the implementation of teaching and learning strategies, teachers become more effective in the presence of an empowering leader. Furthermore, it is argued that a leader must be committed to empowering others so they can support each other in their efforts to make a strategy succeed. Reading develops the minds of the youth, and it requires a leader who is not just strong but also empowered and able to direct the school toward its goal.

Table 4. Influence of Leadership Empowering Behavior on Reading Comprehension Strategies

2*Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	P Value	Remarks
	B	Beta			
Leadership Empowering Behavior	.836	.893	28.621	.000	Significant

Note: $R=.893^a$, $R^2=.797$, $F\text{-Ratio}=819.147$, $P\text{ Value}=.000$

Table 4 presents the results of the regression analysis, the purpose of which is to show the significant influence of leadership-empowering behavior on reading comprehension strategies. The results indicate that leadership-empowering behavior significantly predicts reading comprehension strategies. The findings were apparent in the regression analysis results, where 79.7 percent of the variance of the reading comprehension strategies was explained by the leadership empowering behavior as indicated by $R^2 = .797$. This means that 20.3 percent of the variation can be attributed to other factors not included in this study. Based on the findings, there is a need to consider the leadership behavior of the administrators in the school as this significantly affects the effectiveness of reading

comprehension strategies of teachers in school. Day-Heggie (2021) argued that school administrators not only lead and manage a school but are also required to be strong instructional leaders to strengthen elementary school administrators’ ability to become more effective instructional leaders in assisting teachers with instructional practices to increase student reading achievement. Moreover, she emphasized that positive social change includes elementary school administrators’ increased instructional leadership abilities to impact reading achievement positively. Dreambox Learning by Discovery Education (2019) emphasized that school leaders can cultivate a culture of literacy and keep teachers and students engaged in effective literacy instruction.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study is to determine whether leadership-empowering behavior is a significant predictor of the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies. The researcher selected the 210 school teachers in Cluster 13, Division of Davao City, as the respondents. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey ques-

tionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure the high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: The extent of leadership-empowering behavior in Cluster 13, Division of Davao City, has an overall mean of 4.24 and a descriptive rating of extensive.

Also, leadership-empowering behavior in delegating authority, accountability, self-directed decision-making, information sharing, skill development, and coaching for innovative performance obtained mean scores of 4.26, 4.26, 4.13, 4.33, 4.27, and 4.13, respectively. The extent of effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies in Cluster 13, Division of Davao City has an overall mean of 4.26 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies in terms of facilities, funding, reading resources support, reading clinic objectives, instructional strategies, assessment techniques, intervention activities, and monitoring and evaluation obtained mean scores of 4.28, 4.16, 4.29, 4.39, 4.18, 4.14, 4.27, and 4.32, respectively. The result denotes that leadership-empowering behavior was statistically significantly related to the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies ($r = .893$, $p < .05$). The results indicate that leadership-empowering behavior significantly predicts the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies. The findings were apparent in the regression analysis results, where 79.7 percent of the variance of the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies was explained by leadership-empowering behavior, as indicated by $R^2 = .797$. This means that 20.3 percent of the variation can be attributed to other factors not included in this study.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The analysis's results could conclude that the degree to which the students' leadership-empowering behavior in terms of delegation of authority, accountability, self-directed decision-making, information sharing, skill development, and coaching for innovative performance was extensive and thus oftentimes observed. The analysis's results concluded that the degree to which the reading comprehension strategies were effective in terms of facilities, funding, reading resources support, reading clinic objec-

tives, instructional strategies, assessment techniques, intervention activities, and monitoring and evaluation was extensive and thus oftentimes observed. There was a significant relationship between leadership and effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies. The leadership-empowering behavior significantly predicted the effectiveness of reading comprehension strategies.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: The Department of Education may consider the findings of this study because they could provide them with perspective on how to address teachers' needs, especially in ensuring the effectiveness of their reading comprehension strategies and interventions. School heads may consider fostering leadership-empowering behavior among their educators and administrators. This may include providing professional development programs emphasizing leadership skills and strategies that empower teachers and students. They may encourage their teacher to participate in a collaborative and supportive school culture where teachers are empowered to take leadership roles and support one another. This can create a positive learning environment that enhances reading comprehension strategies. This study's findings would benefit school leaders or principals by giving them an idea of how their leadership behavior might affect their teachers' competence and effectiveness in reading comprehension strategies and interventions. Teachers may encourage a re-evaluation of the current steps taken in implementing their reading comprehension strategies and interventions and may Implement assessment and feedback mechanisms to continuously monitor and improve leadership-empowering behavior within the school. Regular evaluations can help identify areas for growth and development. Likewise, may Invest in ongoing professional development for educators to enhance

their leadership and instructional skills. This idea and an additional contribution to their ref-
can help effectively implement strategies that erences for future research in the field of educa-
empower students in the learning process. Fu- tion.
ture Researchers may use this study as a source

5. References

- 12.5: *Behavioral approaches to leadership*. (2021). Business LibreTexts. [https://biz.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Management/Book%3A_Organizational_Behavior_\(OpenStax\)/12%3A_Leadership/12.05%3A_Behavioral_Approaches_to_Leadership](https://biz.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Management/Book%3A_Organizational_Behavior_(OpenStax)/12%3A_Leadership/12.05%3A_Behavioral_Approaches_to_Leadership)
- Adonis, L. B. S. M. (2020). *Pupils' problem not literacy but reading comprehension – deped – inquirer news* [INQUIRER.net]. Retrieved June 5, 2024, from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1230013/pupils-problem-not-literacy-but-reading-comprehension-deped>
- Afsar, B., & Afsar, B. (2019). Transformational leadership and innovative work behavior. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 23(3), 402–428. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ejim-12-2018-0257>
- Amali, L. N., Bharati, D. a. L., & Rozi, I. F. (2022). The implementation of high order thinking skills (hots) assessment to evaluate the students' reading comprehension achievement. *English Education Journal*, 12(1), 10–18. <https://doi.org/10.15294/eej.v12i1.52571>
- Arianne Merez, A.-C. N. (2019). Palace: Poor reading comprehension of pinoy students a 'reality'. <http://surl.li/tllrh>
- Ärlestig, H. (2008). *Communication between principals and teachers in successful schools* [Doctoral dissertation, Pedagogiska Institutionen UMEÅ UNIVERSITET]. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:142460/fulltext03>
- Brevik, L. M. (2019). Explicit reading strategy instruction or daily use of strategies? studying the teaching of reading comprehension through naturalistic classroom observation in english 12. *Reading and Writing*, 32(9), 2281–2310. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-019-09951-w>
- Bugwak, E. R. (2022). A path analysis of teacher effectiveness as estimated by leadership behavior, communicative competence and self-efficacy of teachers in san isidro, davao oriental. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Studies*, 4(1), 131–142. <https://doi.org/10.32996/>
- Cedeño, M. S. A., & Billones, M. G. (2021). School reading clinic: A reading intervention to support care for non-readers (cnr) program. *Global Scientific Journals*, 9(11). <http://surl.li/tlltz>
- Delegation: The impact of delegation and its benefits*. (2023). London School of Management Education. <https://lsme.ac.uk/blogs/delegation-the-impact-of-delegation-and-its-benefits/#:~:text=Delegation%20promotes%20empowerment%20that%20is,management%20of%20the%20educational%20institution.>
- DeSilver, D. (2020). *U.s. students' academic achievement still lags that of their peers in many other countries*. <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2017/02/15/u-s-students-internationally-math-science/>
- Duke, N. C., Ward, A. E., & Pearson, P. D. (2021). The science of reading comprehension instruction. *The Reading Teacher*, 74(6), 663–672. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.1993>

- Elleman, A. M., & Oslund, E. L. (2019). Reading comprehension research: Implications for practice and policy. *Policy Insights From the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 6(1), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732218816339>
- Financial sustainability*. (2023). Ealing Grid for Learning. Retrieved April 16, 2023, from <https://www.egfl.org.uk/finance-and-data/funding-and-finance/financial-sustainability>
- Gordon, L. (2019). *Funding and support for your struggling reader - helping children to read*. <https://www.helpingchildrentoread.com/articles/funding-and-support-for-your-struggling-reader/>
- Gutierrez, E. (2020). *Monthly monitoring and validation of reading assessment: Its effectiveness in improving the reading*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344541981_MONTHLY_MONITORING_AND_VALIDATION_OF_READING_ASSESSMENT_ITS_EFFECTIVENESS_IN_IMPROVING_THE_READING_PERFORMANCE_OF_GRADES_1_AND_2_PUPILS_OF_BANTIGUE_ES
- Hawley, W. A. (1921). The effect of clear objectives on the teaching of reading. *Journal of Educational Research*, 3(4), 254–260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.1921.10879155>
- Helman, L. A., & Burns, M. K. (2008). What does oral language have to do with it? helping young english-language learners acquire a sight word vocabulary. *The Reading Teacher*. <https://doi.org/10.1598/rt.62.1.2>
- The importance of a parent/guardian's role in their child's literacy: Resources and tips*. (2022). Reading Partners. <https://readingpartners.org/blog/the-importance-of-a-parent-guardians-role-in-their-childs-literacy-resources-and-tips/>
- The importance of reading*. (2023). NORD ANGLIA INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL AL KHOR. <https://www.nordangliaeducation.com/our-schools/al-khor/parent-resources/our-school-ewsletter/primary/the-importance-of-reading>
- The importance of teacher collaboration*. (2017). A-State Online. <https://degree.astate.edu/articles/k-12-education/importance-of-teacher-collaboration.aspx>
- Ingersoll, R. M., Sirinides, P., & Dougherty, P. M. (2018). Leadership matters: Teachers' roles in school decision making and school performance. *The American Educator*, 42(1), 13. <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1173452.pdf>
- Jokisaari, M., & Vuori, J. (2018). Leaders' resources and newcomer socialization: The importance of delegation. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 33(2), 161–175. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jmp-09-2016-0274>
- Jose, R., & Raja, B. W. D. (2011). Teachers' role in fostering reading skill: Effective and successful reading. *Journal on English Language Teaching*, 1(4), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.26634/jelt.1.4.1599>
- Keyser, A. (2022). *The importance of reading skills why is reading important?* WorksheetCloud — Download CAPS School Worksheets South Africa. <https://www.worksheetcloud.com/blog/why-is-reading-important/>
- Lapuz, M. C. L., & Pecajas, E. S. (2022). School heads' authority, accountability, and empowerment as functions of school performance. *Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6701039>
- Laster, B. (2013). A historical view of student learning and teacher development in reading clinics. In *Literacy research, practice and evaluation* (pp. 3–20). Emerald Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/s2048-0458\(2013\)0000002004](https://doi.org/10.1108/s2048-0458(2013)0000002004)

- Loughran, J. (2019). *Pedagogical reasoning: The foundation of the professional knowledge of teaching*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2019.1633294>
- McLaughlin, M. (2012). Reading comprehension: What every teacher needs to know. *The Reading Teacher*, 65(7), 432–440. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.01064>
- McMaster, K. L., Baker, K., Wanzek, J., Hugh, M. L., & Sargent, K. (2021). Professional development to support teachers' implementation of intensive reading intervention: A systematic review. *Remedial and*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-019-09951-w>
- Meador, D. (2019). *Problems for teachers that limit their overall effectiveness*. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/problems-for-teachers-that-limit-their-overall-effectiveness-3194679>
- Mihaly, K. (2019). *Leadership matters: How to help principals promote teaching effectiveness*. <https://www.rand.org>
- Naidoo, P. (2019). Perceptions of teachers and school management teams of the leadership roles of public school principals. *South African Journal of Education*, 39(2), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v39n2a1534>
- Rennie, J. (2014). *Teaching reading comprehension* [Lecture notes distributed in EDF3306 Literacy at Monash University] [Accessed 25 August 2014].
- Sam-Kalagbor, V. O. (2021). Availability and utilization of school reading facilities and student academic achievement in rivers state university. *International Journal of Innovative Social Science Education Research*, 9(2). <https://seahipaj.org/journals-ci/june-2021/IJISSER/full/IJISSER-J-15-2021.pdf>
- Shea, M. (2017). *Reading with understanding: A global expectation*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1158259>
- Zhou, H. (2022). *Why does writing good learning objectives matter?* Duke Learning Innovation. <https://learninginnovation.duke.edu/blog/2017/03/learning-objectives/#:~:text=Learning%20objectives%20should%20be%20used,they%20are%20actionable%20and%20measurable.>